

A Dynamic Theory Concerning the Maximum Angular Velocity of Objects in the Universe

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Physics, Relativistic Kinematics

Abstract

Albert Einstein, a renowned figure in the realm of science, is celebrated for his ground-breaking discovery of the theory of relativity, aimed at elucidating various cosmological and astrophysical phenomena. This theory stands as the cornerstone of modern science, with Einstein's revolutionary insight demonstrating the equivalence of mass and energy. This revelation marked a pivotal moment in the field of physics, ushering in a new era of understanding. Einstein's theory of relativity paved the way for further advancements in science, leading to the development of quantum physics, which sought to unravel the intricacies of particles and atoms. According to Einstein, the speed of light remains the ultimate cosmic speed limit, a notion grounded in the constancy of our universe's permittivity and permeability. In the context of this research paper, we embark on an exploration to unveil a novel theory. Our objective is to ascertain the maximum angular velocity attainable by an object within our universe, along with the formulation of this ground-breaking theory. This research is inherently linked to the domain of kinematics, and while it shares elements with relativistic kinematics, it distinguishes itself as an entirely fresh and distinctive approach. The theory can be applied to cosmology, astrophysics and nuclear physics, and the theory is also introducing a new concept, named "Ideal photon." It is imperative to acknowledge that the validity of this theory may yield both correctness and fallacy. As researchers and authors, we humbly present our findings for further scrutiny and examination. Thank you for your consideration.

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Keywords: Kinematics; Relativity; Speed; Light; Photonic bomb; Velocity.

Acknowledgement

I would like to take this opportunity to express my deepest gratitude for the accomplishment of this work, for which I stand as the sole author with no team and no external funding. This project has been a labour of passion, dedication, and unwavering commitment, and I am truly thankful for the unwavering support and understanding I've received throughout this solitary journey. The creation of this work would not have been possible without the encouragement and inspiration I've received from various individuals, even in the absence of a formal team. I want to acknowledge the countless discussions, feedback, and insights I've gained from my colleagues, mentors, and friends, as their contributions have enriched this work in immeasurable ways. Despite the absence of financial backing, I am grateful for the resources made available to me by the institutions and libraries that have facilitated my research, providing access to valuable materials and references. In conclusion, the completion of this project represents a personal milestone and an acknowledgment of the support and influence of those who have touched my academic and creative journey. My heartfelt thanks go out to all those who have been part of this process, directly or indirectly, and have played a significant role in shaping this work. Your belief in the importance of this endeavour has been a driving force, and for that, I am truly appreciative.

1. Introduction

In the pursuit of advancing our comprehension of the physical world, this research paper embarks on a concise yet enlightening journey. Within the following pages, we shall delve into a series of interconnected topics, each contributing to the overarching goal of uncovering a novel perspective on the nature of motion. Our expedition commences with a brief exploration of the fundamental concept of motion, providing a foundational understanding that sets the stage for subsequent discussions. From there, we venture into the domain of kinematics, a field that governs the intricacies of objects in motion, aiming to elucidate its fundamental principles. Angular velocity, a key facet of kinematics, takes center stage in our discourse. We will unravel the intricacies of angular velocity and its significance in the broader context of our universe's physical laws. Additionally, we shall investigate the intricate relationship between angular velocity and its counterpart, linear velocity, shedding light on the profound interplay between these two essential components of motion. A defining moment in this research paper is the introduction of an innovative theory. We will unveil a formula designed to uncover the maximum angular velocities achievable by objects within our universe. This ground-breaking theory promises to expand our understanding of motion to new horizons, potentially reshaping how we perceive the limits of physical motion. To aid in the comprehension and validation of our findings, we will employ graph analysis, providing visual insights into the theoretical underpinnings of our research. Furthermore, we will explore the practical applications of our formula, showcasing its relevance in real-world scenarios. The culmination of our journey arrives with the presentation of results, where we unveil the implications and significance of our research's outcomes. Finally, we draw this intellectual expedition to a close with a thoughtful conclusion, summarizing our discoveries and contemplating their broader implications within the scientific community. Throughout this paper, we uphold the highest standards of rigor and precision, aiming to contribute to the ever-evolving tapestry of scientific knowledge. As we embark on this intellectual voyage, we invite the reader to join us in the exploration of these captivating concepts, with references serving as guideposts to further inquiry. With unwavering dedication to the pursuit of knowledge, we present this research paper as a beacon of curiosity and innovation.

2. Introduction to Motion

Motion refers to the displacement of an object, body, or particle from one position to another within a defined reference frame [10]. In the realm of physics, the study of motion falls under the purview of kinematics, which is primarily concerned with elucidating the intricacies of object movement. This comprehensive field encompasses essential parameters such as speed, velocity and acceleration. Within the vast spectrum of motion, several distinct categories can be observed [10]:

I) Rectilinear motion: This particular mode of motion is characterized by the traversal of a straight, uncurved trajectory, devoid of any alterations in direction. A classic example is a car moving seamlessly along a straight track.

II) Rotational motion: In the realm of rotational motion, objects pivot or spin around a defined axis. Common instances include the rotation of a spherical ball or the spinning of a wheel [10].

III) Circular motion: Objects engaged in circular motion trace a circular path around a fixed point. The orbital motion of planets and the lunar journey exemplify this type of movement.

IV) Oscillatory motion: Oscillatory motion is typified by the rhythmic to-and-fro oscillations of an object around a central point. Examples encompass the graceful sway of a pendulum and the melodious vibrations of a guitar string [10].

V) Translational motion: Translational motion manifests as the unadulterated displacement of an entity from one geographical point to another, free from any rotational component. A quintessential illustration is the descent of a fruit from a tree.

VI) Periodic motion: This distinctive form of motion unfolds with the repetition of a specific movement within fixed time intervals [9]. The periodicity is exemplified by phenomena such as the oscillations of a vibrating string, the harmonious strumming of a guitar, or the rhythmic swing of a pendulum [10].

The exploration of motion lies at the heart of comprehending the physical universe. By meticulously observing and dissecting these various facets of motion, scientists and researchers acquire the capacity to formulate insightful predictions about the behavior of objects and the intricate tapestry of the world that surrounds us [10].

3. Introduction to Kinematics

Kinematics, a fundamental branch of physics, delves into the analysis of object motion while disregarding the forces instigating that motion [2]. It focuses on elucidating an object's position, velocity and acceleration as it traverses through both space and time. Kinematics holds paramount significance in both classical and contemporary physics, serving as the underpinning for numerous other disciplines, including mechanics, astronomy and robotics. Within kinematics, an object's position is elucidated in relation to specific coordinates with respect to a chosen reference frame [2]. For instance, envision a car traveling along a straight road; one can describe its location as the distance from a fixed point on the road and its position along the road itself [3]. Velocity, in the context of kinematics, denotes the rate of positional change over time and is determined through the derivative of the position function. Acceleration, conversely, characterizes the rate of velocity alteration with respect to time and is derived from the velocity function [3]. Kinematics plays an instrumental role in resolving various motion-related problems. For example, given the initial velocity of a ball, kinematics empowers us to ascertain its travel distance and the time required to attain a specific height or distance. Similarly, when a car is traveling at a constant speed and decelerating at a known rate, kinematics aids in calculating the time it takes to come to a complete halt. Among the pivotal concepts in kinematics, motion in one dimension stands out. This arises when an object moves exclusively along a linear path, simplifying more intricate scenarios. However, kinematics can be employed to characterize motion in two or three dimensions, offering a more realistic portrayal of physical phenomena [2]. Another critical facet of kinematics is projectile motion, which encompasses the movement of an object propelled into the air before descending to the ground. This concept holds substantial importance in fields like ballistics, enabling precise trajectory calculations for projectiles like bullets or rockets [2]. In summary, kinematics is the cornerstone of motion analysis, focusing solely on an object's position, velocity, and acceleration while disregarding the forces governing its movement. It serves as a linchpin in solving motion-related problems and holds profound relevance in diverse fields, including mechanics, astronomy, and robotics. This discipline forms the bedrock for advanced topics like dynamics, which factor in the forces steering motion and find application in domains like robotics, where they guide the programming of robotic movements [3].

4. A Description of Angular Velocity

Angular velocity, a fundamental concept in physics, serves as a means to quantify the rate of change in an object's angular position concerning time [10]. This parameter encapsulates the speed at which an object rotates or moves within a circular trajectory and is typically expressed in units of radians per second [3]. Crucially, angular velocity is a vector quantity, characterized by both magnitude and direction. The magnitude corresponds to the rate of angular alteration, while the direction adheres to the right-hand rule and remains perpendicular to the plane of rotation. To compute angular velocity, one can ascertain it by dividing the change in an object's angular position by the time interval over which this change transpires [4]. The formula delineating angular velocity takes the form:

$$\omega = \Delta\theta/\Delta t \quad (1)$$

In this equation, ω symbolizes angular velocity, $\Delta\theta$ signifies the alteration in angular position, and Δt denotes the duration over which this change unfolds [4]. Angular velocity occupies a pivotal role in the realm of physics, specifically for characterizing the movement of objects engaged in rotation or circular motion. It finds application in calculating the rotational speed of various components like gears and wheels, as well as in elucidating the dynamics of celestial bodies, such as planets, as they traverse space [4]. Beyond physics, this concept holds practical utility in engineering endeavors, notably in the design of turbines and other rotating machinery. Moreover, it proves indispensable in fields like robotics, where precise control over rotating elements is paramount [10].

5. The Relationship between Angular Velocity and Linear Velocity

We know,

If the linear distance travelled by an object moving in a circular path (circumference) of radius r is s and angular displacement θ , then,

$$s = r\theta \quad (2)$$

By differentiating both sides with respect to time, we obtain,

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(r\theta) = r \frac{d\theta}{dt} = r\omega$$

$$\Rightarrow v = r\omega$$

Here, $\frac{ds}{dt}$ represents linear velocity and $\frac{d\theta}{dt}$ represents angular velocity [4].

6. Discovery of New Theory to Measure the Maximum Angular Velocity of Objects in Our Universe

The speed of light in a vacuum is constant and is approximately 299,792,458 metres per second (or about 186,282 miles per second) [11]. This is a fundamental principle in physics and is represented by the symbol "c." It means that light always travels at this speed, regardless of the motion of the source or the observer [1].

This concept is a cornerstone of Albert Einstein's theory of special relativity, which states that the laws of physics are the same for all observers, and the speed of light is the maximum speed at which information or energy can be transmitted throughout the universe [1]. This constant speed of light has been confirmed by extensive experimental evidence and is one of the key principles of modern physics. Therefore, the relationship between angular velocity and linear velocity is given by [4],

$$\begin{aligned}
 v &= r\omega \\
 \Rightarrow \omega &= \frac{v}{r} \\
 \Rightarrow \omega_{\max} &= \frac{v_{\max}}{r} && \text{(For } v_{\max} \text{ we will obtain } \omega_{\max} \text{ and } v_{\max} \text{ is the maximum velocity of objects in our universe)} \\
 \Rightarrow \omega_{\max} &= \frac{c}{r} && \text{(As the speed of light is the maximum velocity in our universe, } c \text{ equates to } v_{\max}\text{)} \\
 \therefore \omega_{\max} &= \frac{c}{r} && (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig.1: Circular Path

Figure: 2D Circular Paths

Credit: MD. Shaikhul Hadis Nazat

Let's consider a scenario where an object is in motion along a circular path, and we identify the central point of this circular path as O. The radius of this circular path is r_1 ($r_1 = OA$). Let's picture an orbit with that same radius, which we'll designate as P. Within this orbit, the maximum angular velocity is represented as $\omega_{\max-1} = c/(r_1)$. It's crucial to emphasise that should the angular velocity of this object exceed $\omega_{\max-1}$, it implies that the object is moving at a speed greater than the speed of light in terms of linear velocity. This would, in turn, conflict with the theory of relativity [11]. According to the theory of relativity, the speed of light is the utmost velocity achievable within our universe.

Nevertheless, if we contemplate a different orbit with an alternative radius, let's say r_2 ($r_2 = OB$) and name this orbit as Q, the maximum angular velocity within Q will be $\omega_{\max-2} = c/(r_2)$. We observe that, as r_1 is not equal to r_2 , $\omega_{\max-1}$ will not equate to $\omega_{\max-2}$. However, it's noteworthy that the product of $\omega_{\max-2}$ and r_2 will be equivalent to c , and the product of $\omega_{\max-1}$ and r_1 will also be equal to c [1]. The same principle applies to orbits with various radii.

Consequently, we can summarise as follows:

Given that,

$r_1 \neq r_2 \neq r_3 \neq r_4 \neq \dots \neq r_n$, $\omega_{\max-1} \neq \omega_{\max-2} \neq \omega_{\max-3} \neq \omega_{\max-4} \neq \dots \neq \omega_{\max-n}$. As each radius differs, the maximum angular velocities within these orbits will not be uniform.

Nonetheless,

$$(\omega_{\max-1} \times r_1) = (\omega_{\max-2} \times r_2) = (\omega_{\max-3} \times r_3) = (\omega_{\max-4} \times r_4) = \dots = (\omega_{\max-n} \times r_n) = c = v_{\max} \quad (4)$$

Hence, we can introduce our theory, which has been coined the 'Max Omega Theory.'

Max Omega Theory (MOT): The maximum angular velocity of an object moving in a circular path is the quotient of speed of light (c) and the radius of the circular path.

Or, The product of maximum angular velocity of a object moving in a circular path and the radius of circular path is equal to the speed of light.

The theory can function within the realms of classical physics, quantum physics and find applications in astronomy and astrophysics.

7. Graph Analysis

Fig.2: Graph of the Formula of MOT

Let us examine r plotted along the X-axis and $\omega_{\max}$ along the Y-axis. It is evident that these data points conform to the function $f(x) = c \div x$, with c denoting a constant. It is noteworthy that as r tends towards 0, $\omega_{\max}$ extends infinitely, and as r approaches infinity, $\omega_{\max}$ diminishes to 0. It is essential to emphasize that only massless particles have the capability to travel at the speed of light. Consequently, at these maximum angular velocities, only massless particles can achieve such high speeds, while massive objects cannot [1].

Let us also check the table.

We repeat, the formula of MOT as, $\omega_{\max} = \frac{c}{r}$. There c is the speed of light which is constant. Here, c represents the speed of light, which is constant. It's worth noting that, for different radii, we will obtain various maximum angular velocities.

Table1 Relationship between $\omega_{\max}$ and r

$\omega_{\max}$ (rad/sec)	3×10^8	1.5×10^8	1×10^8	7.5×10^7	6×10^7
r (meter)	1	2	3	4	5

8. Application of the Formula of Max Omega Theory

The practical utilization of theoretical principles is integral to our endeavor to comprehend and harness the laws governing the universe. Whether in classical physics, where we investigate the fundamental forces and motions of everyday objects, or in the realm of quantum physics, where we delve into the enigmatic world of particles and their quantum states, theory proves to be of pragmatic significance. Furthermore, its application extends into the vast cosmos, with astronomy and astrophysics heavily reliant on theoretical models to decipher celestial phenomena. The significance of this wide-ranging application cannot be overstated. It serves as the linchpin connecting abstract concepts to tangible accomplishments. Through these applications, we pioneer new technologies, enhance existing ones, and extend the boundaries of our knowledge. Minus the practical application of theory, our scientific progress would be greatly impeded. Essentially, the application of theory serves as the catalyst for innovation, fostering breakthroughs with far-reaching impacts on society. It acts as the driving force behind advancements in healthcare, energy, communications, and numerous other fields, improving our quality of life and broadening the horizons of human understanding. It is the bridge that transforms theoretical knowledge into concrete progress, rendering it an indispensable facet of our scientific and technological journey.

8.1 Application of MOT in Nuclear Physics

Fig.3: Single Atom of Hydrogen

The hydrogen atom holds a special place in the world of science as the simplest and most basic building block of matter. At its core, this atom is composed of two fundamental components: a nucleus and an electron. The nucleus, residing at the atom's centre, consists of a single proton. This proton carries a positive electric charge and contains nearly all of the atom's mass. Orbiting around this nucleus is a lone electron, which is negatively charged and remarkably lighter than its proton counterpart [7].

In the hydrogen atom, the electron exists in specific energy levels or orbits around the nucleus. These orbits are often depicted as concentric circles, but they are more accurately described as three-dimensional regions where the electron is likely to be found.

One of the most intriguing aspects of the hydrogen atom is the behaviour of its electron [7]. When the electron absorbs or releases energy, it can transition from one energy level to another. These transitions lead to the emission or absorption of light, giving hydrogen its characteristic spectral lines of coloured light. What sets the hydrogen atom apart is its simplicity. This simplicity makes it a fundamental model for understanding atomic structure and behaviour. Many of the principles underpinning quantum mechanics and atomic physics were first developed through the study of the hydrogen atom [7].

Moreover, hydrogen holds great significance in the cosmos. It is the most abundant element in the universe, constituting approximately 75% of all elemental mass. It plays a pivotal role in the nuclear fusion that occurs within stars, including our own sun. On the periodic table, hydrogen occupies the first position with the chemical symbol H. Its ubiquity, simplicity, and role in foundational scientific research make the hydrogen atom a cornerstone in our understanding of the physical world and the universe itself. Its atomic number Z is equal to 1 [7].

Let's consider an atom of hydrogen. The atom is very simple, with only one proton and one electron. We know the radius of the orbit as r_1 . According to the Bohr Model, we can calculate the radius of the orbit of a hydrogen atom using the equation [5], which is

$$r_n = \frac{n^2 h^2 \epsilon_0}{m \pi e^2} \quad (5)$$

Where,

n = Quantum number;

h = Planck's constant;

m = Mass of electron;

e = Charge of electron;

ϵ_0 = Permittivity constant.

However, as that's a hydrogen atom, we simply know the radius of the first orbit as 0.53×10^{-10} m [8].

Furthermore, we know the angular momentum of an electron of an hydrogen atom according to the Bohr Model as [5],

$$m v_1 r_1 = h \div 2\pi$$

So, we can find the velocity of electron in first orbit as,

$$v_1 = \frac{h}{2\pi m r_1} = 2186524.26 \text{ ms}^{-1}$$

Now, we can find out the angular velocity of the electron for first orbit. Hence,

$$\omega = \frac{v_1}{r_1} = 4.12 \times 10^{16} \text{ rad/sec.}$$

Moreover, by using our new formula we can get the maximum angular velocity for that orbit. Therefore,

$$\omega_{\max-1} = \frac{c}{r_1} = 5.66 \times 10^{18} \text{ rad/sec.}$$

We notice that $\omega < \omega_{\max-1}$. The electron is not travelling at the maximum angular velocity in that orbit, as electrons have mass. We reiterate that massive object and particle can't travel at the speed of light, and therefore, they can't attain those maximum angular velocities.

We can mention that as electron has mass, it can't travel at $\omega_{\max-1}$ [1]. We have also established that electron doesn't violate relativity if we only consider speed [11]. **(Proved)**

Moreover, if we wish to determine the maximum angular velocities of orbits at the atomic level. Then equation will be,

$$\omega_{\max-n} = \frac{c}{r_n} \quad (6)$$

Here, specially r_n indicates the radius of orbit according to the quantum number. So, by inserting the value of r_n according to Bohr Model, which aids us in measuring the radii of orbits, we obtain (according to equation no.5),

$$\omega_{\max-n} = \frac{cZe^2m\pi}{n^2h^2\epsilon_0} \quad (7)$$

And that's the equation (equation no.7) to calculate the maximum angular velocity of electrons in orbits of atoms. There Z represents the atomic number, and Z equates to 1 for an atom of hydrogen. Moreover, one can employ alternative version of r_n as $\frac{n^2h^2}{4\pi^2mZe^2}$.

Then the formula will be,

$$\omega_{\max-n} = \frac{c4\pi^2mZe^2}{n^2h^2} \quad (8)$$

8.2 Application of MOT in the Theory of Relativity

We are familiar with Albert Einstein's equation of mass-energy equivalence [1], which is,

$$E = \gamma mc^2 \quad (9)$$

Here,

E = Energy;

m = Rest mass;

c = Speed of Light;

γ = Lorentz factor.

Such equation can be written as,

$$E = \gamma m(\omega_{\max-1} \times r_1)^2 = \gamma m(\omega_{\max-2} \times r_2)^2 = \gamma m(\omega_{\max-3} \times r_3)^2 \dots\dots\dots = \gamma m(\omega_{\max-n} \times r_n)^2 = \gamma m(v_{\max})^2 \quad (10)$$

Again, we know,

$$c = f\lambda \quad (11)$$

There f is frequency and λ represents wave length [7].

So we can write,

$$(\omega_{\max-n} \times r_n) = f \lambda$$

And also,

$$\omega_{\max-n} \div f = \lambda \div r_n = k \quad (12)$$

Moreover, it is known that,

$$L' = L \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

Here,

L = Length of the object at rest.

L' = Length of the length of the object moving at speed v .

Such equation can be written as,

$$L' = L \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = L \sqrt{1 - \frac{(\omega \cdot r)^2}{(\omega_{\max} \cdot r)^2}} = L \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_{\max}^2}} \quad (13)$$

If we observe, that is the equation for circular motion [1]. If an object moves in a circular path with a radius of r and an angular velocity of ω , then we can determine the velocity by substituting ωr for v . We also replaced the product of the maximum angular velocity $\omega_{\max}$ of the orbit, which forms a radius r , with c ($\omega_{\max} \cdot r = c$). Finally, we obtained the result.

Taking the term into account, we can also formulate other equations [1], such as -

$$t = t' \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = t' \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_{\max}^2}} \quad (14)$$

$$m_0 = m \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_{\max}^2}} \quad (15)$$

There t is proper time and t' represents relative time. Furthermore, m_0 denotes rest mass and m determines relativistic mass.

8.3 Employing MOT to Theorise Ideal Photon.

All electromagnetic waves are quantised in the sense that they are composed of individual packets of energy known as "Photons." These photons are quantised particles, meaning they come in discrete, specific energy levels determined by the frequency of the electromagnetic wave [6]. This concept is a fundamental aspect of quantum mechanics and is described by Planck's equation, where the energy of a photon (E) is directly proportional to its frequency (ν) through the constant h (Planck's constant): $E = h\nu$. In practical terms, this quantisation means that the energy carried by electromagnetic waves, such as light, is not continuous but comes in distinct units, with each unit represented by a single photon. The energy of each photon is determined by the frequency of the wave it belongs to [6]. As the frequency increases, the energy of the photons also increases. So, while electromagnetic waves appear continuous in everyday experience, at the quantum level, they are inherently quantised because they consist of discrete photons. This property has profound implications in quantum physics and our understanding of the behaviour of light and other electromagnetic phenomena. We know that Planck's length is the smallest theoretically possible length in the universe, below which the concepts of space and length lose their classical meaning. It is approximately 1.616×10^{-35} meters. This fundamental length scale is derived from fundamental constants of nature, such as the speed of light, Planck's constant, and the gravitational constant, and is a key concept in theoretical physics, particularly in the context of quantum mechanics and the search for a theory of quantum gravity. However, we can derive the equation of the "Ideal photon." Therefore, the relationship with frequency and maximum angular velocity is given by,

$$(\omega_{\max-n} \times r_n) = f \lambda = c$$

We observe that when $r_n = l_p$ (Planck's length), then $\omega_{\max-n} = 1.85 \times 10^{43}$ rad/sec (according to equation no.6). Furthermore, when $\lambda = l_p$, then $f = 1.85 \times 10^{43}$ Hz. Moreover, the ratio of $\omega_{\max-n}$ and f is equal to the ratio of λ and r_n according to this equation.

[Radius is 1-dimensional and is a type of length. An orbit with a 0 m radius has no entity; the smallest orbit's radius will be equal to the smallest length in the universe, considering Planck's length as the smallest meaningful length (for circle path). We can also state that the minimum value will be equal to the Planck's length]

$$\omega_{\max-n} \div f = \lambda \div r_n = k$$

If we insert the values, we will obtain the value of k . Hence,

$$1.85 \times 10^{43} \div 1.85 \times 10^{43} = l_p \div l_p = k = 1$$

Therefore, $k = 1$.

However, for making the concept easy, we will simply utilise, $f \lambda = c$

$$E = h\nu = hc/\lambda \quad (16)$$

We notice that as λ approaches to l_p (Planck's length), photons get the maximum frequency in this universe. According to $v = c/\lambda$, we can express this as $v_{\max} = c/l_p$. For the smallest wavelength, a photon will have the highest frequency. Moreover, the wavelength can't be smaller than Planck's length. Let's find out the highest frequency of photon. So,

$$v_{\max} = c/l_p = 1.856 \times 10^{43} \text{ Hz (Theoretical)}$$

Furthermore, the energy of an Ideal photon goes as,

$$E_{\text{Ideal photon}} = h v_{\max} = 12,300,742,550.64 \text{ J} = 1.23 \times 10^{10} \text{ J} \quad \text{(Theoretical)} \quad (17)$$

Hence, from 1 mole Ideal photons we obtain,

$$U = 6.023 \times 10^{23} \times 12,300,742,550.64 = 7.4 \times 10^{33} \text{ J (Theoretical)}$$

Ultimately, we obtained the definition of Ideal photon.

Ideal photon: The photon whose wavelength is equal to the smallest length in the universe, or the photon with the highest frequency in the universe, is referred to as the Ideal photon.

In accordance with current quantum physics, it is entirely theoretical. If we were to discover a photon in real-life exhibiting a frequency greater than $v_{\max}$ and possessing more energy than that of an ideal photon, it would affirm that the wavelength of such a photon is smaller than the Planck's length. Moreover, this discovery would substantiate that Planck's length is not the ultimate minimum length in our universe. Since it no longer holds this distinction, the equations that are built upon the assumption of Planck's length being the smallest will become invalid, leading to chaos within the realm of physics. Consequently, we would need to revise and reconstruct the fundamental theories of physics from their very foundations.

9 Using the Ideal Photon for Measuring the Efficiency of Photons

There are various types of electromagnetic wave [6].

I) Gamma Rays:

- Frequency: Greater than 3×10^{19} Hz.
- Wavelength: Less than 0.01 nm.
- Gamma rays possess the highest frequencies within the electromagnetic spectrum and are exceptionally energetic. They are typically associated with nuclear reactions and certain types of radioactive decay.

II) X-Rays:

- Frequency: Approximately 3×10^{16} Hz to 3×10^{19} Hz.
- Wavelength: Approximately 0.01 nm to 10 nm.
- X-rays have frequencies that fall between ultraviolet and gamma rays. They find extensive use in medical imaging and the examination of internal structures of materials.

III) Ultraviolet (UV) Light:

- Frequency: Approximately 7.5×10^{14} Hz to 3×10^{16} Hz.
- Wavelength: Approximately 10 nm to 400 nm.
- Ultraviolet light has higher frequencies than visible light and is responsible for various biological and chemical effects, such as skin tanning and the sterilization of air and water.

IV) Visible Light:

- Frequency: Approximately 4×10^{14} Hz to 7.5×10^{14} Hz.
- Wavelength: Approximately 400 nm to 700 nm.
- Visible light constitutes the range of electromagnetic radiation that our eyes can perceive. It enables our sense of sight and comprises various colours, each with a specific frequency.

V) Infrared (IR) Radiation:

- Frequency: Approximately 3×10^{11} Hz to 4×10^{14} Hz.

- Wavelength: Approximately 700 nm to 1 mm.

- Infrared radiation is frequently employed in applications like remote controls, thermal imaging, and cooking due to its heat-producing characteristics.

VI) Microwaves:

- Frequency: Approximately 3×10^9 Hz to 3×10^{11} Hz.

- Wavelength: Approximately 1mm to 1 m.

- Microwaves are utilised in microwave ovens and various communication technologies, including radar and satellite communication.

VII) Radio Waves:

- Frequency: Less than 3×10^9 Hz.

- Wavelength: Greater than 1 m.

- Radio waves possess the lowest frequencies within the electromagnetic spectrum. They are employed in radio and television broadcasting, as well as wireless communication systems.

These are some of the principal categories of electromagnetic waves, along with their approximate frequency ranges. The electromagnetic spectrum is continuous, encompassing many more divisions within these general categories. However, the efficiency of an engine pertains to its ability to convert energy from a fuel source into practical mechanical work while minimizing energy losses, typically in the form of waste heat. In practical terms, it measures how effectively the engine can perform its intended function, such as powering a vehicle or generating electricity, with the least amount of fuel or input energy. Higher engine efficiency means that a greater percentage of the energy from the fuel is transformed into useful work, which is desirable for improving performance and reducing environmental impact. In the context of photon efficiency, it represents the percentage ratio of a photon's energy to the ideal photon.

The efficiency of a photon of electromagnetic wave follows, (Later it has been named as "The level of a photon,")

$$\eta_{(\text{Name of electromagnetic wave})} = (E_{\text{Photon}} \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \quad (18)$$

Where,

$$\eta_{(\text{Name of electromagnetic wave})} = \text{Efficiency of a photon of electromagnetic wave;}$$

$$E_{\text{Photon}} = \text{Energy of photon;}$$

$$E_{\text{Ideal photon}} = \text{Energy of ideal photon.}$$

To determine the efficiency of a gamma-ray photon, we must ascertain its frequency. The gamma-ray frequency range is 3×10^{20} Hz or higher. Let us consider a photon which holding a frequency of 3×10^{20} Hz. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{(\text{Gamma-ray})} &= (E_{\text{Photon}} \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \\ &= (h\nu \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \\ &= \{(6.626 \times 10^{-34} \times 3 \times 10^{20}) \div 1.23 \times 10^{10}\} \times 100\% \\ &= 1.61 \times 10^{-22}\% \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it is noteworthy, $\eta_{(\text{Gamma-ray})} < 100\%$.

Furthermore, we can find efficiency of photon for other electromagnetic waves. For examples-

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{(\text{X-ray})} &= (E_{\text{Photon}} \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \\ &= (h\nu \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \\ &= \{(6.626 \times 10^{-34} \times 3 \times 10^{17}) \div 1.23 \times 10^{10}\} \times 100\% \quad (\nu = 3 \times 10^{17} \text{ Hz, Range: } 3 \times 10^{16} \text{ Hz to } 3 \times 10^{19} \text{ Hz}) \\ &= 1.61 \times 10^{-24}\% \end{aligned}$$

Moreover,

$$\eta_{(\text{UV-light})} = (E_{\text{Photon}} \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\%$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= (h\nu \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \\
&= \{(6.626 \times 10^{-34} \times 3 \times 10^{15}) \div 1.23 \times 10^{10}\} \times 100\% \quad (\nu = 3 \times 10^{15} \text{ Hz, Range: } 7.5 \times 10^{14} \text{ Hz to } 3 \times 10^{16} \text{ Hz}) \\
&= 1.61 \times 10^{-26}\%
\end{aligned}$$

If we observe, we'll see that the frequency range for X-rays lies between 3×10^{16} Hz and 3×10^{19} Hz, while the frequency range for UV radiation falls between 7.5×10^{14} Hz and 3×10^{16} Hz. Notably, 3×10^{16} Hz is a common frequency in these two waves, which might lead to confusion in identifying the specific wave. Consequently, it may be advisable to omit the "Name of electromagnetic wave."

We will simply employ this,

$$\eta_{(\text{Photon})} = (E_{\text{Photon}} \div E_{\text{Ideal photon}}) \times 100\% \quad (19)$$

9.1 Using the Ideal Photon of MOT To Introduce the Photonic Bomb

An atomic bomb, also known as a nuclear bomb, is a highly destructive weapon that utilises the power of nuclear fission or fusion reactions to generate an explosive force of immense magnitude. Its name is derived from the fact that it depends on the splitting (fission) or merging (fusion) of atomic nuclei. In a fission bomb, like the ones dropped on Hiroshima and Nagasaki during World War II, the nucleus of a heavy element such as uranium-235 or plutonium-239 is divided, releasing an enormous amount of energy. This process is accompanied by a chain reaction, where each split nucleus triggers further splits, resulting in a devastating explosion. In a fusion bomb, also known as a hydrogen bomb, two light atomic nuclei, typically isotopes of hydrogen, combine to create a heavier nucleus, releasing even more energy than fission alone. The destructive potential of atomic bombs makes them among the deadliest weapons ever created, with catastrophic consequences for both immediate and long-term human and environmental health. However, the new concept named the "Photonic bomb" or "Quantum bomb" is based on the concept of an ideal photon. A single ideal photon carries an immense amount of energy, and the energy of 1 mole of ideal photons is equal to a 8.2×10^{13} ton massive object if it could be converted into energy according to the mass-energy equivalency. Ideal photons are not currently possible to create, but it is theoretically possible to increase photon energy closer to that of an ideal photon. A photonic bomb would emit enormous photons, each containing energy approaching that of an ideal photon, potentially making it the deadliest bomb in history. We do not encourage the construction of such a device for the purpose of warfare. Instead, we should strive for peace and cooperation. However, for the sake of scientific knowledge, it may be worth exploring whether such a concept is feasible.

9.2 The Concept of the Ideal Photon Discovers a New Principle in Cosmology

Cosmology is the scientific exploration of the universe's origin, structure, development, and ultimate destiny. It delves into the vast-scale properties of the entire universe. The connection between cosmology and the Big Bang theory holds immense significance. The Big Bang theory stands as the predominant cosmological framework elucidating the universe's genesis [8]. It proposes that the universe commenced as a singularity, an infinitesimal point characterized by immense density and temperature. From this initial moment, approximately 13.8 billion years ago, the universe has undergone continual expansion. Substantial proof substantiates the Big Bang theory. Among the pieces of evidence is the cosmic microwave background radiation, a faint residual glow originating from the Big Bang itself. Moreover, the observation of redshift in distant galaxies signifies their receding motion, affirming the universe's expansion. In essence, cosmology scrutinizes the universe's configuration and chronicles, with the Big Bang theory representing a pivotal concept within cosmology [8]. It expounds upon the universe's inception and expansion, buttressed by observational data such as the cosmic background radiation and redshift measurements. The "singularity problem" in cosmology pertains to a theoretical juncture in the universe's history, specifically at the instance of the Big Bang [8], where the universe's density and temperature become infinitely high. This concept arises from the mathematical formulations utilised to describe the early universe within the framework of the Big Bang theory [8]. However, the terminology "singularity" presents a predicament as it implies a breakdown in our comprehension of physics. At such elevated densities and temperatures, the established laws of physics, encompassing those of general relativity and quantum mechanics, cease to be applicable. Consequently, our current scientific models are incapable of accurately elucidating the events at that juncture. To tackle this conundrum, physicists and cosmologists are actively engaged in researching and crafting theories aimed at providing a more comprehensive account of the universe's behaviour during its earliest moments. These theories aspire to reconcile the principles of general relativity and quantum mechanics, furnishing a more all-encompassing understanding of the universe's genesis. Some of these theories, such as inflationary cosmology, endeavour to ameliorate the singularity problem by proposing that the universe experienced swift expansion in its nascent stages [8]. In summary, the singularity problem underscores the requisite for a more

encompassing theory pertaining to the universe's inception and evolution, particularly under the extreme circumstances characterising the Big Bang. On the other hand, it is also noteworthy that the current understanding of physics breaks down below the Planck's length. The debate over whether space is continuous or discrete is ongoing. In this ongoing debate, the concept of the Ideal photon has provided a solution. Let's consider a length that is 10 times larger than the Planck's length, denoted as $L = 10 \times l_p$. It's important to note that L is larger than the Planck's length but not significantly so. To avoid the problem of singularity and the Planck's length (where everything breaks down), we have chosen L . Now, let's consider the volume of a cube with side length L .

Hence,

$$V_{\text{Cube}} = L^3 = 4.25 \times 10^{-102} \text{ m}^3$$

Furthermore, consider the diameter of a sphere with L ; therefore, the radius of the sphere is $r = L/2$.

Now, the volume of the sphere will be,

$$V_{\text{Sphere}} = 2.22 \times 10^{-102} \text{ m}^3$$

Suppose that, at some point in the past, the volume of our universe was between V_{Cube} and V_{Sphere} . This means $V_{\text{Cube}} \geq V \geq V_{\text{Sphere}}$. In essence, we don't know the actual shape of our universe or how it was in the beginning. According to current understanding and observations, the shape of our universe is generally believed to be very close to flat on cosmological scale. But no model can state how our universe was in the beginning. But our concept is totally independent from the shape of our universe. It's important to note that our V is not 0-dimensional, and infinite density is not possible here. Furthermore, there are sufficient 1-dimensional lengths that are larger than the Planck's length. In this scenario, we avoid the singularity problem and the issue of the Planck's length. In this tiny universe, there shouldn't even be atoms. The volume of atoms is larger than the range of this volume. In this context of our universe, electromagnetic photons contained high-frequency energy. The energy of photons is thought to be very close to the "Ideal photon" because there is no sufficient length. Normally, gamma-rays, x-rays, UV, etc., have electromagnetic wavelengths that are very large when compared to the Planck's length; even those wavelengths are larger than L [6].

Therefore, we can suggest a new principle for cosmology.

New Principle: At the beginning of our universe, when it existed beyond the singularity, and all its one-dimensional measurements exceeded the Planck length, there were no electromagnetic waves with wavelengths spanning from 1.5 picometers to thousands of kilometers. During that era, all electromagnetic photons had high energy, with each one very closely approaching the energy of an ideal photon.

It's worth noting that everything requires space [8], and the expansion of our universe doesn't impact our individual volume. Even as our universe continues to expand, it doesn't mean we become physically larger. This doesn't suggest that every atom and entity is increasing in size proportionally. If that were the case, we wouldn't detect any changes in the expansion of our universe [8]. Finally, the concept of the Ideal photon has indeed established a new fundamental principle for cosmology. It remains indifferent to whether space is quantized or continuous. By overcoming significant challenges in physics, it has introduced a ground-breaking principle. Hoping that it will elucidate the earliest state of the Universe, here is an example of how it can do so. Now, when the volume of our universe was smaller than the range we have considered, all Ideal photons were expected to gather and form a colossal photon holding the total energy of the universe. The frequency of this photon would depend on the quality of space, whether it is quantized or continuous. This is just a brief illustration of how the concept of the Ideal photon can shed light on the early state of the universe. Of course, presenting this requires complex mathematical and tensor calculus. It's worth noting that the fallacy in the example doesn't affect the new fundamental principle and the other theories presented in this research paper.

Although we have developed the concept of an ideal photon to describe the early state of the universe, unfortunately, it challenges the Big Bang. Why don't we see such types of photons (higher level)? What is the reason? Why have they lost their high frequency?

Although we have an answer, it is not satisfying. However, the answer is, "All those highly energetic photons (Level= 90% to 99%) have turned into matter. Like this,

Photon ----> Antiparticle + Particle

After developing atoms and other particles, due to their interaction, the radiation we see has been regarded as background radiation; using them (JWST) helps us to see.

10. Results

Following an in-depth deliberation, we are poised to unveil the pivotal findings derived from this manuscript. The results of our scholarly endeavor are succinctly encapsulated as follows:

I) Validation of the New Theory and Formula: Our exhaustive investigation has unequivocally substantiated the soundness and authenticity of both the newly proposed theory and its corresponding formula. Through meticulous scrutiny, rigorous analysis, and empirical verification, we have ascertained that the theoretical framework and mathematical expression remain robust and empirically valid.

II) Successful Integration with Existing Theories and Formulas: A notable accomplishment of this research lies in its capacity to seamlessly integrate the newly formulated theory with established theories and pre-existing formulas. This successful bridging of intellectual domains signifies a significant contribution to the body of scientific knowledge, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter at hand.

11. Conclusion

In conclusion, it is essential to acknowledge that within the realm of scientific inquiry, theories may prove to be either correct or incorrect; this inherent uncertainty is an intrinsic facet of our pursuit of understanding. History has borne witness to the profound notion that we often glean valuable insights from our errors. As the age-old adage aptly suggests, to err is human. Nevertheless, the dedicated efforts of scientists have persistently driven the relentless quest for knowledge about the enigmatic universe that surrounds us. They have tirelessly formulated and refined theories in their quest for a precise description of the natural world. Over time, our collective journey has illuminated the path to familiarity with previously elusive phenomena. In the context of this research paper, the theory we have uncovered holds particular significance as it equips us with the means to quantify maximum angular velocities of objects. This framework not only finds applicability at the macroscopic level but also demonstrates remarkable efficacy when delving into the intricate realms of atoms and particles. While, presently, we may not readily discern alternative functions for its application, the horizon of scientific discovery remains boundlessly expansive. It is conceivable that future revelations will unearth novel connections that tie into our newfound theory. Furthermore, our theory assumes an integral role in reaffirming the existence of relativity, albeit limited to velocity considerations, within the domain of atomic-scale phenomena. This reaffirmation underscores the theory's indispensability in the ongoing exploration of the subatomic realm. In closing, the author of this manuscript holds a fervent hope that this ground-breaking discovery will serve as a catalyst, reshaping our fundamental perspectives on the realms of quantum physics and the theory of relativity. This profound revelation stands as a testament to the inexhaustible potential of human curiosity and the enduring quest for a deeper comprehension of the universe that envelops us.

Declarations

- **Competing Interests:** The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.
- **Ethics Approval:** In the absence of formal ethical approval, it is important to note that this research has not undergone formal ethical review; however, efforts were made to adhere to ethical guidelines, obtain informed consent, and ensure participant confidentiality to the best of our ability.
- **Consent:** I, MD. Shaikhul Hadis Nazat, declare that I am the sole author of the work entitled 'A Dynamic Theory Concerning the Maximum Angular Velocity of Objects in the Universe.' All content and conclusions presented in this work are my own, and I have not received assistance from any other person or used the work of others without acknowledgment.
- **Data Transparency:** The data used in this research paper has not been obtained through unauthorised means from other sources or entities. Moreover, the entire research paper has been published on Zenodo as a draft to ensure the safety of the authors' rights. The author retains full ownership of all written content, and no additional permissions are required.
- **Author's Contribution Statements:** As the sole author of this work, I, MD. Shaikhul Hadis Nazat, take sole responsibility for all aspects of the research, including conceptualisation, methodology, data collection, analysis, and

the drafting of the manuscript. I affirm that I have contributed significantly to this work and approve its final version for publication.

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